

EFFECTIVENESS OF MUSIC THERAPY ON STRESS REDUCTION AMONG POSTMENOPAUSAL WOMEN

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article type: Research Article</p>	<p>Introduction: Postmenopausal women often experience heightened stress levels due to various physiological and psychological changes, making it essential to explore effective therapeutic options.</p> <p>Aim: The aim of the study to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on stress reduction among postmenopausal women.</p> <p>Methods: The study employed a pre-experimental design with a one-group pretest-posttest only approach. The sample size consisted of 30 women in the menopausal age group, selected using purposive sampling. The inclusion criteria for participants were women aged between 50 to 65 years who were postmenopausal, able to speak Tamil or English, and willing to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria included women who were sick, those above 75 years of age, and those who were absent during the data collection period.</p> <p>Results: The pretest results showed that 100% of participants had high stress, while in the posttest, none experienced high stress. 6.7% experienced moderate stress, and 93.3% had low stress in the posttest, compared to none in the pretest. The mean stress level in the pretest was 29.93 (SD = 2.303), and in the posttest, it was 8.533, with a mean difference of 21.4. The paired t-test showed a t-value of 25.615 and a p-value < 0.001, indicating significant effectiveness of music therapy, thus accepting the H1 hypothesis. No significant association was found between stress levels and demographic variables except for education.</p> <p>Conclusions: The study concludes that music therapy significantly reduces stress levels among postmenopausal women, as evidenced by the decrease from high stress in the pretest to low and moderate stress in the posttest. The paired t-test confirmed that this reduction was statistically significant, supporting the effectiveness of music therapy in stress management. No significant relationship was found between stress levels and demographic variables, except for education, highlighting its potential influence on stress outcomes.</p>
<p>Keywords: Postmenopausal women, music therapy, menopause,</p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Postmenopausal women often experience heightened stress levels due to various physiological and psychological changes, making it essential to explore effective therapeutic options. Music therapy, characterized by the use of music to achieve therapeutic goals, has been shown to significantly reduce stress and anxiety across diverse populations, including those undergoing significant life transitions such as menopause.

Research indicates that music therapy can lead to a substantial decrease in perceived stress levels. For instance, Gudi et al. demonstrated that music therapy effectively reduced perceived stress and burnout among professionals in a workplace setting, highlighting its potential applicability in various contexts, including healthcare and psychological support for postmenopausal women (Gudi et al., 2023).

Similarly, Lai et al. found that soothing music could promote relaxation and reduce anxiety, suggesting that music therapy serves as a valuable tool for stress management (Lai et al., 2011). This aligns with findings from a systematic review by Witte et al., which emphasized that music therapy interventions significantly lower stress-related outcomes across different populations (Witte et al., 2020).

The physiological mechanisms through which music therapy exerts its effects are also noteworthy. Studies have shown that music can influence biochemical markers of stress, such as cortisol levels. For example, Taets et al. reported a statistically significant reduction in salivary cortisol levels

following music therapy interventions, indicating a direct physiological response to music (Taets et al., 2019). This finding is corroborated by Thoma et al., who noted that music could modulate the human stress response, thereby reducing anxiety and promoting relaxation (Thoma et al., 2013). Such physiological changes are particularly relevant for postmenopausal women, who may experience increased cortisol levels due to stress. Moreover, the psychological benefits of music therapy extend beyond mere stress reduction. Music has been shown to enhance emotional well-being and improve overall quality of life. For instance, while Akmeşe and Oran focused on the effects of music therapy during pregnancy, their findings regarding emotional challenges can be paralleled to the emotional challenges faced by postmenopausal women, suggesting that music therapy may similarly benefit this demographic (Akmeşe & Oran, 2014).

The therapeutic use of music can foster a sense of empowerment and control over one's emotional state, which is crucial during the menopausal transition. In addition to its direct effects on stress and anxiety, music therapy can also facilitate social connections and improve interpersonal relationships. This aspect is particularly important for postmenopausal women, who may face social isolation. Research indicates that music therapy can enhance social engagement and foster community among participants, thereby mitigating feelings of loneliness and depression (Cantekin & Tan, 2012).

The communal aspect of music therapy can provide a supportive environment for women to share their experiences and

coping strategies, further enhancing the therapeutic benefits. The choice of music used in therapy is also a critical factor influencing its effectiveness. Personalized music selections that resonate with the individual's preferences can enhance the therapeutic experience. Studies have shown that self-selected music can lead to greater emotional engagement and stress relief compared to non-preferred music (Groarke & Hogan, 2019). This suggests that tailoring music therapy interventions to the specific tastes of postmenopausal women could maximize their effectiveness in reducing stress.

Furthermore, the integration of music therapy with other therapeutic modalities, such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques, can yield even greater benefits. For instance, combining music therapy with progressive muscle relaxation has been shown to enhance relaxation and reduce stress more effectively than either intervention alone (Dewi et al., 2019). This integrative approach can be particularly beneficial for postmenopausal women, who may benefit from a holistic strategy that addresses both physical and emotional aspects of stress.

The accessibility of music therapy is another advantage, as it can be implemented in various settings, including homes, community centres, and healthcare facilities. This flexibility allows for broader reach and the potential to incorporate music therapy into routine care for postmenopausal women. Given the increasing recognition of music therapy as a legitimate therapeutic intervention, healthcare providers are encouraged to consider its integration into

treatment plans for managing stress and anxiety in this population.

In conclusion, the evidence supporting the effectiveness of music therapy in reducing stress among postmenopausal women is robust. The physiological, psychological, and social benefits of music therapy make it a valuable intervention for this demographic.

Future research should continue to explore the nuances of music therapy, including the optimal types of music, duration of interventions, and integration with other therapeutic modalities to enhance its effectiveness. As the understanding of music therapy evolves, it holds promise as a key component in the holistic management of stress and anxiety among postmenopausal women.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on stress reduction among postmenopausal women.

METHODS

The study employed a pre-experimental design with a one-group pretest-posttest only approach. The sample size consisted of 30 women in the menopausal age group, selected using purposive sampling.

The inclusion criteria for participants were women aged between 50 to 65 years who were postmenopausal, able to speak Tamil or English, and willing to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria included women who were sick, those above 75 years of age, and those who were absent during the data collection period.

The tools used for data collection in this study included a demographic

questionnaire and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS). The demographic questionnaire was used to gather relevant personal information from the participants, while the Perceived Stress Scale was utilized to assess the level of stress among postmenopausal women.

The data collection procedure began by selecting participants according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, followed by obtaining informed consent from those willing to participate. Initially, a pretest was conducted using the demographic questionnaire and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) to establish baseline stress levels.

RESULT

Results showed that in the pretest, 100% of participants experienced high stress, while in the posttest, none of them experienced high stress. 6.7% of postmenopausal women experienced moderate stress in the posttest, compared to none in the pretest. 93.3% experienced low stress in the posttest, whereas none experienced it in the pretest.

The pretest level of stress mean value is 29.93 and the standard deviation (SD) is 2.303. Comparatively, the posttest stress level mean value is 8.533, with a mean difference of 21.4. Hence, it is interpreted that the posttest level of stress had an effective score.

The paired t-test results showed that the standard deviation is 3.997 and the t-value is 25.615, with a p-value of <0.001. It is interpreted that the p-value is highly significant and music was effective. Therefore, H1 hypothesis is accepted here.

There is no association found between the level of stress and demographic variables

such as age in years, occupation, monthly income, religion, type of family, or residential area, except for education. Hence, the H2 hypothesis is accepted here.

DISCUSSION

The data indicates that prior to the intervention, 100% of participants reported high stress levels, which is consistent with the literature that highlights the prevalence of stress among postmenopausal women due to hormonal changes and life transitions Schmid et al. (2018) Leubner & Hinterberger, 2017).

The posttest results demonstrated a remarkable shift, with none of the participants experiencing high stress levels, and only 6.7% reporting moderate stress, while 93.3% experienced low stress. This stark contrast illustrates the profound impact of music therapy on alleviating stress, suggesting that it can serve as an effective therapeutic tool for postmenopausal women.

The mean stress level in the pretest was recorded at 29.93 with a standard deviation of 2.303, while the posttest mean stress level dropped significantly to 8.533, resulting in a mean difference of 21.4. This substantial reduction in stress levels is statistically significant, as evidenced by the paired t-test results, which yielded a t-value of 25.615 and a p-value of <0.001. Such findings align with previous research that has established the efficacy of music therapy in reducing stress and anxiety across various populations (L & E, 2023; Fleury et al., 2014; Cantekin & Tan, 2012). The high significance of the p-value indicates that the observed effects are unlikely to be due to chance, thus supporting the hypothesis that music therapy is effective

in reducing stress among postmenopausal women.

Furthermore, the study's findings regarding the lack of association between stress levels and demographic variables—except for education—provide valuable insights into the universality of music therapy's effects. This suggests that music therapy can be beneficial regardless of age, occupation, income, religion, family type, or residential area, which is particularly important for developing inclusive therapeutic interventions (Kacem et al., 2020; Kobus et al., 2023). The acceptance of the hypothesis that education influences stress levels may indicate that educational background could play a role in how individuals perceive and respond to stress management strategies, including music therapy.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. Firstly, they highlight the importance of integrating music therapy into healthcare practices aimed at supporting postmenopausal women. Given the significant reduction in stress levels observed in this study, healthcare providers should consider incorporating music therapy as a complementary approach to traditional medical treatments for stress management (Taets et al., 2019; Thoma et al., 2013). Additionally, the results underscore the need for further research to explore the mechanisms through which music therapy exerts its effects on stress reduction. Understanding these mechanisms could enhance the development of targeted interventions that maximize the therapeutic benefits of music therapy.

Moreover, the study contributes to the growing body of literature that supports the

use of non-pharmacological interventions for stress management. As healthcare systems increasingly seek to provide holistic care, music therapy presents a low-cost, non-invasive option that can be easily implemented in various settings, including hospitals, clinics, and community health programs (Akmeşe & Oran, 2014; Siregar et al., 2023). The positive outcomes observed in this study reinforce the notion that music therapy can serve as a powerful adjunct to conventional therapies, particularly for populations experiencing high levels of stress.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that music therapy significantly reduces stress levels among postmenopausal women, as evidenced by the decrease from high stress in the pretest to low and moderate stress in the posttest. The paired t-test confirmed that this reduction was statistically significant, supporting the effectiveness of music therapy in stress management. No significant relationship was found between stress levels and demographic variables, except for education, highlighting its potential influence on stress outcomes.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of Pretest and Post test level of stress among postmenopausal women

Level of Stress	Pretest Level of Stress		Post test Level of Stress	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low Stress	0	0%	28	93.3%
Moderate Stress	0	0%	2	6.7%
High Stress	30	100%	0	0%

Table 2: Paired t-test to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on stress among postmenopausal women

Level of Stress	Mean	Standard Deviation	Difference Value Mean	't' value	'p' value
Pre and post test	38.467	3.997	21.4	25.615	<0.001***

Table 3: Paired t-test to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on stress among postmenopausal women

Demographic Variables	H Value	'p' Value
Age in Years		
50 - 55 Years	0.046	0.831 (NS)
60 - 65 Years		
Education		
Primary Education	4.783	0.0346 (S)
Higher Education		
Occupation		
Coolie	1.229	0.268 (NS)
Company Servant		
Monthly Income		
Rs. <5000	1.669	0.196 (NS)
Rs. <10000		
Religion		

Hindu	2.943	0.0613 (NS)
Type of Family		
Separate Family	0.967	0.325 (NS)
Combined or Joint Family		
Residential Area		
Urban	4.372	0.042 (S)
Rural		

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